

Reduction of BrO_3^- with Urea and Thiourea

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The reduction of BrO_3^- with urea and thiourea in perchloric acid ($\text{pH} < 2$) medium at room temperature (25°) has been studied. Stoichiometries of the reactions have been deduced to be

IN the Belousov-Zhabotinskii reaction¹, potassium bromate, by way of its reduction, is the source of bromine which brominates in presence of an acid and a metal ion catalyst. Therefore, the reduction of bromate has become a point of interest for current research workers.

Quite recently, the oligo-oscillatory behaviour of the uncatalysed reaction between bromate and thiourea has been studied². The origin of oscillations relies on the $[\text{Br}_2]/[\text{Br}^-]$ ratio. In general, the reactions of bromate with urea and thiourea have been found to be quite complex. In most cases stoichiometries of the bromate-thiourea reactions are difficult to establish because they often depend on the ratio of the concentration of thiourea to the oxidant³. We report here the reduction of bromate with urea and thiourea as reductants in perchloric acid ($\text{pH} < 2$) medium at room temperature (25°).

Experimental

Potassium bromate (Riedel), urea (BDH), thiourea (BDH) and perchloric acid (70–75%) were used as such. Potentiometric titrations were performed by modified method⁴. Solutions of potassium bromate ($M/60$), urea ($M/60$) and thiourea ($M/140$) were prepared in perchloric acid. The bromate solution (10 ml) was taken in a number of reaction vessels and then required volume of the urea solution was added to each reaction vessel in increasing order. The potentiometric readings were taken. Similar set of experiment was performed in case of titration between the bromate solution (10 ml) and required volume of the thiourea solution. All readings were taken at room temperature after 15 min storage of the reaction mixture. The redox potentials were also recorded against time. The potentiometric readings were taken by using a platinum electrode with a double junction calomel reference with 10% ammonium nitrate as the contact electrolyte. The spectrophotometric readings were taken on a uv spectrophotometer. Stoichiometries of the reactions were obtained by

gravimetric determination of sulphate ions produced. Nitrogen evolved was measured and bromine was estimated from its absorbance at λ_{max} 390 nm.

TABLE I—POTENTIOMETRIC DATA OF REDUCTION OF BROMATE WITH UREA/THIOUREA IN BATCH ENVIRONMENT

[H ⁺], M	Storage time min	Position of inflexion ml	Nature of inflexion	E° (mV)	
				Thiourea	Urea
0.05M	15	8.33	Very sharp	800	800
	30, 45, 60	8.33	Very sharp	—	—
0.04M	15	—	—	—	—
	30, 45, 60	8.33	Very sharp	800	800
0.03M	15, 30, 45	—	—	—	—
	60	8.33	Very sharp	800	800

Results and Discussion

In case of reduction of bromate with both urea and thiourea at different concentrations of acid, sharp inflexion was observed at 8.33 ml after 15, 30 and 60 min storage of reaction mixture in 0.05, 0.04 and 0.03 M perchloric acid respectively. This corresponds to five-electron equivalent reduction stage of bromate. The reaction could not proceed further even after the prolonged storage of the reaction mixture. The formation of molecular bromine at this stage was confirmed by the sharp inflexion of redox potential traces (Figs. 1 and 2). The rapid decrease in redox potential in Figs. 1 and 2 corresponds to the commencement of molecular bromine in the absorbance traces in Figs. 3 and 4. From Figs. 3 and 4 it appears that the time taken for the formation of molecular bromine is inversely proportional to the concentrations of bromate and acid. The time of commencement of molecular bromine is smaller in case of thiourea than that of urea. The redox potential remains nearly constant (800 mV) during the course of the formation of molecular bromine. The molecular bromine was estimated at λ_{max} 390 nm and confirmed (Figs. 3 and 4).

Fig 1 Redox potential traces for the reaction between bromate and thiourea in different initial acid concentrations: (○) 0.03, (△) 0.04 and (□) 0.05 MH^+ ; $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0 = 0.01 \text{ M}$, $[\text{CSN}_2\text{H}_4]_0 = 0.005 \text{ M}$.

Fig 2 Redox potential traces for the reaction between bromate and urea in different initial acid concentrations: (○) 0.03, (△) 0.04 and (□) 0.05 MH^+ ; $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0 = 0.01 \text{ M}$, $[\text{CON}_2\text{H}_4]_0 = 0.005 \text{ M}$.

Fig 3. Absorbance traces at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 390 \text{ nm}$ in different initial bromate concentrations: (○) 0.03, (△) 0.04 and (×) 0.05 M BrO_3^- ; $[\text{H}^+]_0 = 0.08 \text{ M}$, $[\text{CSN}_2\text{H}_4]_0 = 0.005 \text{ M}$.

Fig. 4. Absorbance traces at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 390 \text{ nm}$ in different initial bromate concentrations: (○) 0.03, (△) 0.04 and (×) 0.05 M BrO_3^- ; $[\text{H}^+] = 0.08 \text{ M}$, $[\text{CO}(\text{NH}_2)_2]_0 = 0.005 \text{ M}$.

Stoichiometries were determined as

The stoichiometries were valid only under the conditions employed. The ratio of one mole of thiourea and one mole of sulphate produced was found to be constant. Similarly, the ratio of one mole of urea and one mole of nitrogen evolved was found to be constant. Finally, about 95% bromine was obtained from the reaction mixture after about 24 h storage of the reaction mixture.

Though the reduction of bromate to molecular bromine occurs in successive two-equivalent redox process⁶, but we have not observed such reduction of bromate with urea and thiourea, and instead, we

have found that the reduction of bromate to molecular bromine occurs in five-equivalent redox process.

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